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ABSTRACTS

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Identification of candidate biomarkers for recurrent ovarian cancer prognosis by integrated analysis of RNA-Seq and microarray data

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Abstract: According to American cancer society, the year 2022 has seen 19,880 patients being diagnosed with ovarian cancer (OC) and 12,810 deaths due to this disease. Over 75% of these cases were detected at advanced stages, requiring urgent surgical intervention and platinum-based chemotherapy. Most of death is due to delay in diagnosis and higher recurrence rate of the disease. In this study we identified recurrence-related differentially expressed genes (DEGs) for OC by integrating RNA Seq dataset and microarray dataset, obtained from TCGA-GDC portal and NCBI-GEO database, respectively. DEG analysis of datasets was performed using Bioconductor R packages DESeq2 and Limma. DEGs observed commonly between the microarray and the RNA seq datasets were selected for further analysis to identify hub genes, their functional analysis and for identifying the protein-protein interaction. Six recurrence related hub genes viz. CXCL1, CCL20, MMP1, IHH, S100A7 and FGF20 were identified and validated by survival analysis. Identified hub genes may have a strong influence on the prognosis of ovarian cancer recurrence and progression. Further, in vitro analysis of these hub genes can help in the identification potential biomarkers and drug targets.

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